

Relation between the Results of Binomial Expansions with Multiple of 2

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Abstract: This paper provides the relationship between the results of binomial expansions which are equal to multiple of 2 with non-negative exponents. The binomial and combinatorial techniques are used in different ways to find the results of binomial expansions and its application in physical and life sciences and management.

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1. Introduction

The traditional coefficient (traditional combination) and innovative coefficient or optimized combination [1 - 8] are given below:

Traditional combination: $nC_r = \binom{n}{r} = \frac{n!}{r!(n-r)!}$, where $n, r \in N \cup \{0\}$ & $N = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$.

Optimized combination: $V_r^n = \frac{(r+1)(r+2)\dots(r+n)}{n!}$, ($n \geq 1, r \geq 0$ & $n, r \in N$).

Here, $V_r^{n-r} = nC_r = nC_{n-r}$ and $V_r^n = pC_r$, where $p = n + r$.

$$V_n^0 = V_0^n = nC_0 = nC_n = 1 \text{ \& } V_0^0 = 0C_0 = \frac{0!}{0!} = 1.$$

2. Results of Binomial Expansion

The following results of binomial expansions [1- 8] that are equal to multiple of 2 with non-negative exponents are given below:

$$(1) \sum_{i=0}^n (i+1)V_i^{n-i} = (n+2)2^{n-1}. \quad (2) \sum_{i=0}^n i \times V_i^{n-i} = n2^{n-1}.$$
$$(3) \sum_{i=0}^n (i-1)V_i^{n-i} = (n-2)2^{n-1}. \quad (3) \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} = 2^n.$$

These results are useful in natural science, engineering and medicine [9]

3. Relations between Binomial Expansions

Relation 1: $\sum_{i=0}^n (i+1)V_i^{n-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n (i-1)V_i^{n-i} = \sum_{i=0}^n i \times V_i^{n-i} = n2^{n-1}.$

Proof: Let us simply the general terms in the two parts of binomial expansions (Relation 1) as follows:

$$(i + 1)V_i^{n-i} + (i - 1)V_i^{n-i} = 2iV_i^{n-i}. \text{ This idea can be applied for Relation 1.}$$

$$\sum_{i=0}^n (i + 1)V_i^{n-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n (i - 1)V_i^{n-i} = 2 \sum_{i=0}^n iV_i^{n-i} = (n + 2)2^{n-1} + (n - 2)2^{n-1} = 2n2^{n-1}.$$

$$\text{Then, } 2 \sum_{i=0}^n iV_i^{n-i} = 2n2^{n-1} \Rightarrow \sum_{i=0}^n iV_i^{n-i} = n2^{n-1}.$$

Relation 2:
$$\sum_{i=0}^n (i + 1)V_i^{n-i} - \sum_{i=0}^n (i - 1)V_i^{n-i} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} = 2^n.$$

Proof: Let us simply the general terms in the two parts of binomial expansions (Relation 2) as follows:

$$(i + 1)V_i^{n-i} - (i - 1)V_i^{n-i} = 2V_i^{n-i}. \text{ This idea can be applied for Relation 2.}$$

$$\sum_{i=0}^n (i + 1)V_i^{n-i} - \sum_{i=0}^n (i - 1)V_i^{n-i} = 2 \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} = (n + 2)2^{n-1} - (n - 2)2^{n-1} = 4 \times 2^{n-1}.$$

$$\text{Then, } 2 \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} = 22^n \Rightarrow \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} = 2^n.$$

Hence, two relations are proved.

4. Conclusion

We discussed the binomial and combinatorial technique including optimized combination (innovative binomial coefficients) and also, the relations between binomial expansions that is equal to multiple of two with non-negative exponents provided with explanation and proofs. These binomial and combinatorial techniques will be of immediate interest to a broader readership of researchers in computational science.

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